

Anticipatory sustainability assessment framework for material development demonstrated on material selection for bio-based benzoxazine synthesis

Jan-Marten Sprenger^{a,b}, Gideon Abels^a, Katharina Haag^a, Mohammad Fahad Zaki Khan^a, Katharina Koschek^{a,*}

^a Fraunhofer-Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM, Wiener Strasse 12, Bremen D-28359, Germany

^b University of Bremen, Faculty of Production Engineering, Badgasteiner Strasse 1, Bremen D-28359, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Conventional life cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies, including recent prospective approaches for emerging technology assessment, are still facing challenges in managing uncertainty and stakeholder involvement. These limitations highlight the need for streamlined, integrative, proactive, and yet holistic approaches. This work fills the gap with the development of the Sustainable Tool for Anticipatory and Participative Material Development (Mat-STAP) as a novel assessment approach. Inspired by the streamlined LiSET assessment tool, the SURF-UK sustainability framework and the principles of Green Chemistry, Mat-STAP provides an anticipatory, and semi-quantitative assessment framework for holistic and integrative decision-making in material development. The methodology focuses on framing, process visualisation, high-level sustainability indicators, and a simplified assessment matrix to promote understanding, collaboration, and transparency. The present work starts with a conventional LCA of bio-based benzoxazine and glass fibre composites as a substitute of steel, demonstrating its lack of significance for early technology assessment during innovative material development. Mat-STAP is then applied to a case study on the synthesis of bio-based benzoxazines for composite applications, to evaluate the potential of different bio-based phenolic feedstocks for a sustainable benzoxazine biopolymer. Allyl phenol followed by phloretic acid emerge as the most promising candidates. Mat-STAP aims to bridge a gap between the conventional LCA and innovative material development, offering a proactive and collaborative assessment methodology to identify application-specific sustainable solutions.

1. Introduction

While materials have been abundantly available and usable without foresight for the past two centuries, today the limitation of resources and environmental impacts of human products and technologies is more than evident, especially in the light of human population growth (Ashby, 2016). This awareness and understanding led to a paradigm shift in the chemical industry during the 1970s and 80s, aiming to reduce the environmental impact of products and processes (Sheldon, 2018). In recent years, the focus has been placed on the development of guidelines and tools to facilitate the transformation towards sustainable development uniting concepts such as design-for-circularity, green chemistry, and sustainability assessments (Moni et al., 2020). The Twelve Principles of Green Chemistry have been introduced by Anastas and Warner in 1998 (Anastas and Warner, 1998) to encompass and promote a priori assessment strategies for more sustainable chemistry and product

development according to the benign by design approach. Early tools such as the *E*-Factor (Sheldon, 2018) and atom economy (Trost, 1991) provided quick-assessment metrics to guide sustainable chemistry. While these tools align with the principles of Green Chemistry, they primarily address environmental aspects, leaving broader sustainability considerations underexplored, such as economic and social dimensions (Moni et al., 2020).

Life-cycle assessment (LCA), standardised by ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 (DIN EN ISO 14040, 2021; DIN EN ISO 14044, 2021), has become the predominant method for environmental evaluation due to its high scientific soundness and structured approach. However, LCA has notable limitations, particularly for early-stage material development (low TRL). It is primarily retrospective, requiring clearly defined system boundaries as well as extensive and robust data to achieve meaningful results (Moni et al., 2020; Yang and Chua, 2009). Early-stage applications of LCA often involve assumptions and extrapolations, leading to uncertainty and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Katharina.Koschek@ifam.fraunhofer.de (K. Koschek).

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potentially misleading results (Alhazmi et al., 2021). Previous studies agree that anticipatory LCA approaches, referred to as emerging technology assessments, proactive, prospective, exploratory, early-stage or ex-ante, require additional work compared to the already extensive traditional LCA, adding rather than reducing complexity (Moni et al., 2020; van der Giesen et al., 2020; Yousefzadeh and Lloyd, 2021; Hetherington et al., 2014). Furthermore, its quantitative nature makes LCA less suitable for incorporating qualitative aspects such as stakeholder engagement or application-specific performance goals, which are critical for sustainable material development at low TRL (Mccool and Stankey, 2004; Muazu et al., 2021).

The general shortcomings of the traditional LCA have also been specifically addressed for bio-based materials before, which are playing a key role in sustainable development (Yang and Chua, 2009; Pawelzik et al., 2013). Existing LCAs of biomaterials are significantly based on assumptions, causing uncertainty and imbalances when compared with known fossil based materials (Yang and Chua, 2009). Additionally, the integration of performance metrics with sustainability indicators remains a challenge. Therefore, Le Duigou and Baley (Le Duigou and Baley, 2014) proposed integrating specific mechanical properties of biocomposites with LCA. They, along with Miller et al. (Miller et al., 2013), stressed the need for incorporating sustainable parameters already during the design phase rather than after production. The application of the twelve principles of Green Chemistry for the development and evaluation of more sustainable phenolic resins has been presented by Jones (Jones, 2020).

To address these gaps, anticipatory sustainability assessment frameworks incorporating multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods have been developed (Zhang et al., 2017; De Farias et al., 2022). Examples include the LiSET methodology by Hung et al. (Hung et al., 2020), which enables environmental evaluations for emerging technologies and an iterative transition towards traditional LCA, and the SURF-UK framework by Bardos et al. (Bardos et al., 2011), which emphasizes stakeholder involvement in land remediation projects. Aside from this, several approaches exist for MCDM applied to material selection, which consider criteria related to sustainability (Zhang et al., 2017; Stojčić et al., 2019). However, as the ones mentioned, many existing frameworks still lack a holistic perspective, crucial for sustainable decision making, and the flexibility to address multi-product, layered material designs, incorporating diverse sub-product and sub-process-specific requirements, as well as material requirements to meet application-specific performance goals.

The present work introduces the Mat-STAP methodology, a Sustainable Tool for Anticipatory and Participative Material Development, designed as framework specifically for early-stage material development. Mat-STAP provides an anticipatory, LCA based approach with reduced complexity, considering application-specific requirements, stakeholder input, economic and ecological constraints, and uncertainties. It aims to enhance the sustainability of early-stage decisions while enabling a collaborative, comprehensible workflow grounded in stakeholder participation and constructivist decision-making. Being related to MCDM, the Mat-STAP methodology employs the weighted sum model (WSM), which has been identified as one of the most robust, simple, and transparent methodologies for MCDM (Markatos et al., 2023). Different to existing anticipatory assessment methodologies, Mat-STAP takes a holistic approach to sustainable early-stage material and process selection, balancing comprehensive evaluation with reduced complexity to facilitate stakeholder involvement. In addition to offering the transparency and structure needed to screen a wide range of early-development candidates, Mat-STAP supports the entire layered, dynamic, and iterative material development process. The tool is designed not only for material selection but also as a complementary framework to guide and refine each stage of the layered, dynamic, and iterative material development process.

Mat-STAP will be applied to the development of innovative bio-based benzoxazine resins for composite applications as substitute to

fossil based materials. Benzoxazines are thermosetting polymers with inherent flame retardance making them attractive for a variety of applications with high fire safety requirements, such as the aerospace, automotive and shipbuilding industries (Wolter et al., n.d.; Machado et al., 2021). In addition, their high molecular flexibility allows them to be synthesised from a variety of bio-based resources. In comparison to other structural polymers, e.g. epoxides, the use of benzoxazine based polymeric materials is restricted to a limited number of applications. Bio-based benzoxazines have recently been launched to market and have not yet been used on a commercial scale (Abels et al., 2024). Thus, due to missing alternative assessments that could be used for benchmarking, the starting point for the evaluation of the Mat-STAP method will be a conventional LCA approach of bio-based benzoxazine resins, synthesised at low TRL (1–5). By doing so, the challenges of a prospective LCA will be evaluated and addressed with Mat-STAP.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. LCA of bio-based versus fossil based benzoxazine resins

A comparative LCA of bio-based benzoxazine resin synthesis at low TRL (1–5) in comparison to a fossil based benzoxazine was performed according to the standardised methods, as described in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 to compare their environmental impact (DIN EN ISO 14040, 2021; DIN EN ISO 14044, 2021).

2.1.1. Goal and scope definition

The primary goal of the study was to assess the environmental impacts associated with the synthesis of innovative bio-based and fossil based benzoxazine resins. The study aimed to identify environmental hotspots and compare the environmental impact of the synthesis of novel fossil based and bio-based benzoxazines. The scope of the assessment included cradle-to-gate boundaries, focusing on the production phase of benzoxazine resins. The functional unit was defined as 1 kg of benzoxazine resin. In addition to the standardised scope of the LCA, this assessment was done to identify data availability, data quality and data limitations for a quantitative assessment.

2.1.2. System boundaries

The study focuses on the production of three benzoxazine resins, covering the various chemicals involved in the processes. Two bio-based benzoxazines were analysed in comparison to a fossil based benzoxazine. The first was based on Sesamol (Thermo Fischer, 98 %) /1,6-Diaminohexane (S-DAH) (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥ 98 %) and the second was based on priamine (Croda Europe Ltd) /ester made from phloretic acid (TCI Chemicals, > 98 %) and ethanol (Carl Roth, 99.8 %) (3-(4-hydroxyphenyl) propionic acid ethyl ester or phloretic acid ethyl ester) (HPA-EE-priamine). The fossil benzoxazine was based on bisphenol F and aniline (Araldite MT35700, Huntsman, Texas, USA). The laboratory-scale syntheses served as the baseline scenario for the assessment. To approximate industrial-scale production, it was assumed that the use of chemicals and energy would be optimised. Hence, a 90 % solvent recovery rate was estimated based on lab data. In addition, as waste generation was expected to decrease with increasing TRL, only 10 % of the waste generated in the laboratory process was assumed for the assessment. The respective system boundaries are presented in Fig. 1.

2.1.3. Life cycle inventory analysis (LCI)

The datasets for the chemical substances were mostly based on Ecoinvent v3.9 datasets for European production for the year 2023. The data for the bio-based materials were largely based on literature data as well as estimations and proxy processes while the data for the energy consumption of the resin synthesis were solely based on estimates. The data sets, which are based to a significant extent in assumptions and therefore contain notable uncertainties are indicated as presented in Fig. 1. For phloretic acid and diaminohexane, data was only available in

Fig. 1. System boundaries for the material inputs for three different benzoxazine resin synthesis as part of the conventional LCA. Uncertain inputs based on assumptions and approximations are indicated with a question mark.

the literature for the climate change impact category and not for the other impact categories to be assessed according to the EF 3.1 method. Furthermore, no database entries were found for sesamol or priamine in any database at all, so proxy processes based on rape oil and sesame seeds as well as fatty alcohol and ammonia were used. Also, paraformaldehyde had to be replaced with formaldehyde data sets and the bisphenol F component had to be replaced with available data from bisphenol A. No allocation was necessary for this study, as the processes considered did not produce co-products.

2.1.4. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

For the modelling, the software SimaPro 9.5 (PRé Consultants, Netherlands) and the environmental footprint 3.1 method (EF 3.1) was used for evaluation. The results for all 16 impact categories assessed are provided in the SI 3 Fig. S3.

2.1.5. Interpretation

The use of proxy data and assumptions introduces uncertainties that constrain a fully quantitative interpretation of the results. Due to limited data availability for some bio-based materials, the analysis was reduced to a subset of impact categories. While all 16 impact categories were assessed, only the three impact categories particulate matter, ozone depletion and climate change could be assessed on the basis of data that was categorised as robust with regard to the assumptions made. Of these, only climate change was identified as a significant impact for the comparative LCA.

2.2. Development of Mat-STAP method and case study for the selection of bio-based phenol feedstocks for benzoxazine synthesis

The structural flexibility of benzoxazines allow them to be synthesised from various bio-based feedstocks. However, due to the limited commercial availability of bio-based benzoxazines, there is a lack of benchmarks and robust data for and anticipatory material selection using the LCA (Abels et al., 2024). Hence, a novel anticipatory and streamlined methodology, referred to as Mat-STAP, was developed and applied to a case study focusing on selecting bio-based phenol feedstocks for the synthesis of new benzoxazine resin systems at TRL 1. This approach involved the evaluation and selection of bio-based phenol feedstocks through the active participation of relevant stakeholders across the material development value chain, including raw material suppliers, laboratory-scale material developers and scientists, and

industrial experts involved in upscaling as well as manufacturer in the automotive and aviation industry. Collaborative stakeholder input was critical in identifying sustainability indicators and material performance-related requirements that served as the foundation for the feedstock evaluation process. Then, experts in the relevant fields quantified performance goals and state-of-the-art benchmarks based on primary sources, literature, and experience, enabling the comparative rating and assessment of six bio-based phenol feedstocks: allyl phenol, pyrogallol, catechol, phloretic acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, and gallic acid. Also, the rating of the feedstock options was carried out by these experts. Focusing on potential sustainability and performance trade-offs early in the process helps to guide the development towards viable and sustainable solutions even under high uncertainty. At this stage (TRL 1), no functional unit was defined, as the assessment aimed to provide general guidance for material selection rather than specific comparative metrics. The system boundary begins at the raw material extraction and ends after the resin synthesis. The final evaluation was performed using the WSM, which systematically aggregates weighted criteria scores, enabling a balanced and objective evaluation of the feedstocks. This ensured a consistent and repeatable framework for assessing feedstock options while aligning with the anticipatory principles of the Mat-STAP methodology. The results of the assessment, including the defined requirements, performance goals, and criteria, are detailed in the supplementary information (SI) 1 Table S1 and Table S2. These tables outline the sustainability indicators, their associated weights, and the performance benchmarks for each feedstock option.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Conventional environmental assessment for a bio-based versus fossil based benzoxazine

The full results of the traditional LCA methodology applied to emerging technologies such as the synthesis of novel benzoxazine resins according to the EF 3.1 method are provided in the SI 3 Fig. S3. Based on the robustness of data and significance regarding the comparative LCA, only the results of the impact category climate change are shown in Fig. 2. At this low TRL (1–5), no definitive statement can be made regarding the environmental impact of bio-based feedstocks versus fossil based feedstocks. Based on the comparative results of the selected impact category climate change, the fossil based MT35700 benzoxazine shows the lowest impacts (21.9 kg CO₂ eq.), followed by the sesamol

Fig. 2. Selected LCA results of novel benzoxazine resins at low TRL (1–5) for the impact category climate change, represented as absolute values.

derived benzoxazine (S-DAH) (33.4 kg CO₂ eq.) and the phloretic acid derived benzoxazine (HPA-EE-priamine) shows the highest impact overall (87.8 kg CO₂ eq.). With view to the full impact assessment, including less robust and significant categories, the HPA-EE-priamine system still exhibits the highest environmental impact across 13 of all 16 categories. Notably, it shows over 60 % higher impacts compared to the other benzoxazines in the categories climate change, particulate matter, eutrophication, ionising radiation, land use, resource depletion and water. Also, the acidification potential is almost 50 % higher than that of S-DAH and 80 % higher than MT35700. However, differences between S-DAH and MT35700 are less pronounced, with S-DAH still having higher impacts in twelve impact categories. Only in four impact categories, MT35700 exhibits comparatively higher impacts. The non-carcinogenic human toxicity is dominated by S-DAH with an impact approximately 90 % higher than both other benzoxazines. In contrast, the MT35700 system exhibits the highest impacts in the carcinogenic human toxicity and ozone depletion.

However, these results remain subject to a high degree of uncertainty as shown in Fig. 1. For the fossil based MT35700, the exact composition is unknown and the LCA relies considerably on proxy data and assumptions. In addition, also the LCIs for the S-DAH and HPA-EE-priamine systems rely significantly on proxy data. Due to these limitations, the LCA results at this stage can only be used as estimates and cannot be classified as conclusive. While the assessment still provides some comparative insight into the state of the art of such polymers, especially regarding the data availability, the significance of the results for further material development is very limited. Communication and conclusions based on such unreliable results deriving from this conventional assessment approach for emerging technologies might cause false statements or inefficient material development with respect to sustainability and performance objectives. This highlights the need for a methodology that incorporates broader sustainability dimensions, including social and economic factors, particularly under conditions of uncertainty.

3.2. Method development of Mat-STAP assessment

To address the limitations of conventional LCA and expand the scope towards a sustainability assessment, a novel anticipatory methodology, Mat-STAP, was developed. This approach bridges environmental, economic, and social dimensions, building on the principles of life cycle thinking while incorporating streamlined assessment strategies to ensure practical application in early-stage material development. The

method incorporated life-cycle based indicators as well as alternative indicators relevant for emerging technology assessment and early-stage decision-making. The new method is inspired by the SURF-UK sustainability framework for land remediation developed by Bardos et al. (Bardos et al., 2011; Bardos et al., 2018; Bardos et al., 2020) and a streamlined emerging technology assessment methodology proposed by Hung et al. (Hung et al., 2020). It aims to extend limited quick assessment metrics derived from the twelve principles of Green Chemistry and support stakeholder involvement, while enabling significant results regarding sustainability in dealing with uncertainty. (Hung et al., 2020; Bardos et al., 2011; Bardos et al., 2018; Bardos et al., 2020) The new methods' approach can be explained by four steps: (i) the framing to define the scope and limitations, (ii) the structure of the procedure with its key elements and process flow, (iii) the process visualisation and further simplification as part of the preparation phase and (iv) the assessment and selection phase.

The purpose of the framing process is to define the approach and scope of the assessment procedure and to tailor it to the dimensions of the examined project. Bardos et al. (Bardos et al., 2020) defined six key

Table 1

Key Principles from Bardos et al. (Bardos et al., 2011) to guide the SURF-UK sustainable assessment process transferred from material development perspective. The transfer includes an adapted structure of the SURF-UK key-principles according to the prioritisation from a material development perspective, as well as an equivalent translation into the corresponding terminology and specification of their interpretation in the context of this work.

	Key Principles from SURF-UK	Transfer to Mat-STAP
1	Protection of human health and the wider environment	Benign by design approach of Green Chemistry; Proactive sustainable development; Product responsibility
2	Safe working practices	expertise combined with holistic perspective
3	Consistent, clear, and reproducible evidence-based decision-making	Description of scope, boundaries, methodology; Process visualisation; Semi-quantitative assessment matrix for semantic and rationale decision finding process
4	Recordkeeping and transparent reporting	Continuity of practice; Transparency regarding uncertainty
5	Good governance and stakeholder involvement	Simplification; Participation; Collaboration
6	Sound science	Effective combination of subjective and objective knowledge; Supplement relevant data with expertise

principles guiding the SURF-UK sustainable assessment process. In Table 1 the transfer and adaptation of such from a material development perspective are shown.

3.2.1. Mat-STAP key elements classification and process flow

The structure of the Mat-STAP procedure and classification is depicted as an assessment cascade represented by the top-down pyramid in Fig. 3. Any material or product development can be seen as a compromise, synthesis or combination of performance and sustainability along a range spanned by indicators of these two categories. Performance-related indicators can be, for example, the stiffness or strength of materials, while typical sustainability indicators focus on environmental aspects, such as energy consumption or climate relevant emissions from synthesis or production processes. This range, which expands with both categories, will be referred as the Range of Efficiency. In general, all raw material and product choices, as well as material and product developments, can be situated within this Range of Efficiency and can be assessed according to their intrinsic and consequential performance and sustainability using the corresponding indicators. In the early stages of material or product development at low TRL, there are multiple raw material and process options to choose from, the selection of which is decisive for the performance and sustainability of the resulting products. For the presented approach, such optional choices will be called Potential Solutions. In view of this and to address the aforementioned challenges of the conventional retrospective LCA, the presented method adopts a top-down approach, as opposed to conventional LCA assessment. The a priori assessment of material development at low TRL levels starts at the entry-level with the Expert Filter that represents the sustainability management of product development. Sustainability management combines guided sustainability management practices involving at the same time the knowledge and empirical values of experts in the respected field of development. This filter therefore relies on the know-how of the experts for the material development in their respective fields (e. g. chemists, engineers, designers) as well as their awareness of the project goals, market restrictions and social competences. These experts play an integral role in configuring the assessment matrix by defining product and process-specific requirements, as well as defining the Range of Efficiency. As this approach requires interdisciplinary understanding, reproducibility, comprehensibility, and persuasiveness, the decision finding is complemented by the introduction of a semi-quantitative sustainable assessment framework to provide comparative evidence and reproducibility. The approach will be described in detail in the following sections. The methods process flow is divided in eleven consecutive steps which can be assigned to the preparation, assessment, and selection phase and will be described in the following sections (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Visualisation of the procedure as a top-down approach to reduce effort at entry level by using the Expert Filter and the semi-quantitative assessment to promote sustainable solution selection without conducting a full scale LCA inspired by Bardos et al. (Bardos et al., 2011).

Fig. 4. The procedure divided in eleven consecutive steps which can be assigned to the preparation, assessment, and selection phase.

3.2.2. Preparation phase

Framing is an integral part of sustainability assessments and refers to the process of defining the scope, boundaries, context, and perspective from which the assessment will be conducted. It sets the stage for how the sustainability of a product will be assessed and ensures that the assessment is aligned with specific objectives and stakeholder concerns. Therefore it identifies stakeholders of the material or process development as well as their interests and objectives. The framing has a major impact on the transparency of the assessment and the interpretation of the results and drawn conclusions. The framing process is complemented and supported by a process visualisation. This is a powerful tool to improve the understanding and mapping of the product development system. It helps to gain a holistic overview of the process and to simplify complex information. It is further used to identify and track down products and sub-products as well as processes and sub-processes along the value chain. This tool can be used not only for the material development at laboratory level, but also along all product life stages including the use phase and the end-of-life. It is an effective tool to identify impact hot spots as well as directly and indirectly involved interest groups or stakeholders. In addition to directly involved stakeholders, interest groups such as consumers, other industries or even society and the impersonal environment can be indirectly involved and affected by material development.

Since sustainability relates to the three pillars of economy, environment and social aspects, the assessment has to be conducted based on a suitable selection of relevant sustainability indicators of each category. These indicators are generally defining sustainability in the respective category (Bardos et al., 2018; Mesa et al., 2018; Denčić-Mihajlov and Zeranski, 2018). As there are multiple indicators defined by e.g. the European Commission (European Commission, 2024) or the UN (United Nations General Assembly, 2017), summarising and selecting a reduced number of indicators already is an important part of simplification. An adequate selection is essential to measure, assess and identify, both quantitatively and qualitatively, the goals within the scope of the project. While these might have a certain general relevance for sustainable material development, project-specific fine-tuning of the selection is

crucial to ensure an effective and tailored assessment procedure. The selection of a certain set of most relevant impact categories has to be identified for each developmental step along the materials or products value chain. The attribution of these indicators to each requirement is used to calculate the so-called Sustainability Share S_t of each requirement and the product or processes according to eqs. (1)–(3) in order to adjustment the weighting accordingly.

All involved interest groups must agree upon the general performance goals of the developed materials and align respective requirements with the addition of the sustainability guidelines encompassed in the Green Chemistry and the overall general good practice in the light of sustainability. Sustainability criteria as well as material performance measures such as mechanical properties and other requirements of importance to stakeholder interests will be considered. These requirements will be listed in the assessment matrix according to the relating product or process. They become the direct measures of the applied assessment. The adaptive design of the method allows these requirements to be adjusted along the technology development with progressive iterations and based on the current development step or TRL with increasing knowledge gain.

3.2.3. Assessment phase

Each requirement will be weighted and is attributed or linked to the four most relevant sustainability indicators from the selection of overarching high-level indicators by the experts and stakeholders for the respective development step along the value chain that is being assessed. There are several methods for the evaluation of criteria weights, such as the analytic hierarchy process (AHP), the best worst method (BWM) or the analytic network process (ANP), which are altogether categorised as subjective weighting methods (Singh and Pant, 2021). For the present study, the distribution of weights was proposed and agreed by all experts and stakeholders. The definition of the requirement weights is a critical aspect affecting the outcome of the assessment. To evaluate the robustness of the final rankings in relation to changes of the weights, as sensitivity analysis was done and can be found in the SI 2 Table S4 and Fig. S2. The corresponding Sustainability Share S_t can be calculated relative to each requirement and as a total value for the product or process. It provides the percentage of economic, environmental, or social & safety decisions-based evaluations. It shows in other words, which sustainability indicator-category dominates the evaluation of the process. Based on this, it is possible to adjust the weighting of each requirement to promote potentially underrepresented aspects of sustainability according to the development objectives and scope. For each requirement, the sustainability indicators I_{ijn} are classified as economic, environmental, or social. The S_t for each category t (economic, environmental, social) is calculated according to the eqs. (1)–(3) by counting the number of indicators n attributed to each category. The integration within the assessment matrix is shown in Table 2.

$$S_{\text{economic}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Number of Economic Indicators}}{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Total Indicators}} \tag{1}$$

Table 2
Implementation structure for S_t in the assessment matrix.

(Sub-)Product / Process	Product–/ Process specific Requirement	Sustainability Indicator	Sustainability share		
X_i Evaluated Object	C_{ij} Criteria	I_{ijn} Four attributed indicatces (economic, environmental, social)	S_t Number of economic indicators	Number of environmental indicators	Number of social indicators
x_1	c_{11}	i_{111} i_{112} i_{113} i_{114}			
x_2 Σ	c_{21}		S_{economic}	$S_{\text{environmental}}$	S_{social}

$$S_{\text{environmental}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Number of Environmental Indicators}}{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Total Indicators}} \tag{2}$$

$$S_{\text{social}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Number of Social Indicators}}{\sum_{i=1}^I \text{Total Indicators}} \tag{3}$$

The Range of Efficiency forms the basis for evaluating the possible solutions in the assessment matrix and provides expressed measures to increase objectivity whilst dealing with uncertainty. It defines the range between the existing state of the art of a reference material or process and a performance goal with respect to a specific requirement. This can either be expressed in quantitative values or qualitative expressions. It will be integrated in the assessment matrix as specific measures for the performance goal of a requirement $Q_{ij}^{(goal)}$ and the respective performance state of the art $Q_{ij}^{(state)}$ of a reference for the same requirement. Possible solutions will be ranked and placed within this range and rated accordingly for the assessment.

3.2.4. Selection phase

The theoretical concept of the developed assessment matrix is shown in Table 3. A possible solution (option Q_{ij}) will be rated from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent) based on its rank within the Range of Efficiency with respect to a specific requirement C_{ij} . The overall score ($Z^{(k)}$) for an option (k) is calculated according to the following eq. (4). This score is the sum of the products of each requirements weight (W_{ij}) and the respective rating (Q_{ij}) for that option.

$$Z^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^I W_{ij} * Q_{ij} \tag{4}$$

The evaluation of an option can be continued over several process steps and products (X_i), each with their own set of requirements, in order to contribute to a consistent and continuous evaluation process. This will help to identify potential solutions to meet the project requirements, minimise environmental impacts, and promote sustainable practices throughout the material development process. The option with the highest overall score will supposedly be the best suited option in the light of a sustainable material development.

Table 3
Theoretical concept of the developed assessment matrix.

(Sub-) Product / Process	Product–/ Process specific Requirement	Weight	Option #1	Option #2
X_i Evaluated Object	C_{ij} Criteria	W_{ij} Relative Importance of criteria	$Q_{ij}^{(1)}$ Qualitative Rating of Option #1	$Q_{ij}^{(2)}$ Qualitative Rating of Option #2
x_1	c_{11}	w_{11}	q_{11}^1	q_{11}^2
	c_{12}	w_{12}	q_{12}^1	q_{12}^2
	c_{13}	w_{13}	q_{13}^1	q_{13}^2
x_2	c_{21}	w_{21}	q_{21}^1	q_{21}^2
Σ			$\frac{1}{z}$	$\frac{2}{z}$

3.3. Case study: Mat-STAP assessment of bio-based feedstocks for benzoxazine synthesis

A case study for low TRL biomaterial assessment is shown for the selection of bio-based feedstocks for the synthesis of bio-based benzoxazine resin systems, following the presented assessment framework according to Fig. 4. In the case study, the benzoxazine resin systems are developed for the manufacturing of biocomposite parts with recycled carbon fibre fabrics.

3.3.1. Framing

The aim of the semi-quantitative sustainability assessment is to effectively evaluate different bio-based monomers as phenolic feedstocks for the benzoxazine synthesis with respect to the pre-defined product and process requirements for this stage of development (TRL 1–3). This involves assessing biobased feedstocks according to a set of requirements by the measures of selected sustainability indicators, both collectively defined by all stakeholders.

3.3.2. Process visualisation

Fig. 5 shows a graphical representation of the process flow of a biocomposite part made from a bio-based benzoxazine matrix system and recycled carbon fibre fabric. It shows the value chain from cradle-to-grave, which includes the synthesis of the resin system, the production of the reinforcing fibre fabrics, the composite manufacturing, part assembly up to the use phase and the end-of-life scenarios. The process flow in the beginning can be divided into separate value chains, one for the polymer matrix system and one for the reinforcing fabric, which cojoin in the process of the composite manufacturing. The matrix line consists of the raw material extraction, which means the biobased feedstocks in the first place but also process chemicals, followed by the matrix synthesis, and resulting in the biobenzoxazine resin. The parallel fabric line consists of the composite recycling process to acquire the recycled carbon fibres used for the semi-finished product production, resulting in the recycled carbon fibre needle felt fabrics. The process visualisation further marks the system boundary and identifies the main inputs and outputs within each process step.

3.3.3. Selected high-level sustainability indicators

For this case study, further relevant for the preparation phase of Mat-STAP is the project-specific and developmental step-specific selection of 18 representative indicators, six for each sustainability pillar, as shown in Table 4. According to the framework, these indicators were selected and agreed by all stakeholders involved in the case study, which includes chemists and process engineers from the material development perspective, partners from the chemical industry, manufacturers from the product development perspective, and end users from the automotive and aviation industry. According to these measures, the presented case study of the synthesis of bio-based benzoxazines along the material development of biocomposites will be evaluated within each of these identified most relevant impact categories. These overarching sustainability measures will be assigned to each defined requirement in the following Mat-STAP phase.

3.3.4. Requirement weight, indicator attribution and sustainability share

The assessment matrix of the bio-based benzoxazine synthesis, the requirements and requirement weights as well as the respective set of four most-relevant attributed indicators from the high-level indicator selection (see Table 4), is shown in Table 5 using the example of the requirement for recyclability of solvents. The indicator attribution allows for the calculation of the S_b , which represents the ratio of the three

Table 4
Selection of high-level sustainability indicators.

Economic	Environmental	Social & Safety
direct & indirect costs	natural resources and waste	Education
degree of innovation & addition of value	Emissions to air	human health and safety
production efficiency & processability	land use	ethics, equity, social justice
energy consumption	freshwater use	locality (community involvement)
current & future market demand	environmental pollution (soil, ground and surface water)	working conditions
transport	ecology & biodiversity	Culture

Fig. 5. Process visualisation of the value chain of a composite part made from bio-based benzoxazine and recycled carbon fibre felts.

Table 5

Part 1 - Example from the assessment tool with inputs for the bio-based benzoxazine synthesis, showing the resulting S_i of a selected requirement after the indicator attribution.

(Sub-)Product / Process	Product-/ Process specific Requirement	Weight	Sustainability Indicator	Sustainability share		
X_i Evaluated Object	C_{ij} Criteria	W_{ij} Relative Importance of criteria	I_{ijn} Four attributed indicatces (economic, environmental, social)	S_i Number of economic indicators	Number of environmental indicators	Number of social indicators
Benzoxazine Synthesis	recyclability of solvents	5 %	direct & indirect costs production efficiency & processability degree of innovation & addition of value natural resource depletion & waste	3	1	0
Σ				75 %	25	0%

pillars of sustainability (economic, environmental, social & safety) for the respective product or process. After the attribution of indicators for all pre-defined requirements, the overall calculated S_i results in an evaluation dominated by economic aspects with overall 57.5 % share of the attributed indicators, followed by 27.5 % environmental aspects and 15 % social and safety aspects. The complete assessment matrix and inputs are presented in the SI 1 Table S1. The results provide insight into the selection of requirements and the opportunity to adjust the weighting of requirements to meet the project's sustainability and performance objectives. All defined requirements and weights are shown in Table 6.

3.3.5. Range of efficiency

For the same example requirement “recyclability of solvents” from the assessment matrix, the Range of Efficiency is shown in Table 7. The complete inputs are presented in the SI 1 Table S2. For the bio-based benzoxazine synthesis, cardanol was chosen as reference the material for the rating of the bio-based monomer selection. Cardanol is already the phenolic monomer feedstock for numerous successfully synthesised benzoxazines, exhibiting good mechanical properties and high thermal stability. In addition, the raw materials for the production of cardanol are inexpensive and widely available, making it a suitable candidate for large-scale production. (Monisha et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2019)

3.3.6. Anticipatory emerging technology assessment results and selection

As potential raw materials for new bio-based benzoxazine monomers, gallic acid, P-hydroxybenzoic acid, phloretic acid, catechol, pyrogallol, and allyl phenol were evaluated by experts based on the data available in the assessment matrix (see SI 1 Table S3). For each requirement, the different options were ranked between 1 (poor) and 5 (excellent). After rating and calculating the overall weighted score of each potential solution, allyl phenol (score: 3.8) followed by phloretic acid (score: 3.65) show the highest values (Fig. 6). Final scores as comparative normalised absolute and weighted values can be found in the SI 1 Fig. S1. The close overall score of both phenols is due to different

Table 6

Overview of the defined requirements and the weights for the case study.

Process/ Product specific requirement	Weight
low use of auxiliary materials	5 %
good local availability of raw materials	5 %
high process scalability (per reaction)	15 %
low energy intensive process (temperature, time, ...)	10 %
high yield of educt	15 %
low volatile generation during synthesis	5 %
low price of raw materials (plant material)	10 %
high mass availability of raw materials (educts/reactants)	15 %
recyclability of solvents	5 %
high bio-content	15 %

Table 7

Part 2 – Example from the assessment tool and inputs for the “recyclability of solvents” requirement for the bio-based benzoxazine synthesis showing the Range of Efficiency.

(Sub-)Product / Process	Product-/ Process specific Requirement	Range of Efficiency			
		Performance - Goal $Q_{ij}^{(goal)}$ measure	Unit	Performance - State of the art $Q_{ij}^{(state)}$ measure	Unit
X_i Evaluated Object Benzoxazine Synthesis	C_{ij} Criteria recyclability of solvents	100	%	90	%

ratings and weighting for the categories: low energy intensive processes (weight: 10 %), low price of raw materials (weight: 10 %), and high mass availability of the raw materials (weight: 15 %). While the performance of phloretic acid was ranked as intermediate (3) among all three categories, allyl phenol was ranked excellent (5) regarding low energy intensive processes, good (4) for low price of raw materials, but only sufficient (2) for high mass availability of raw materials. As anticipated, the overall outcome of the evaluation is sensitive to the requirement weighting. In comparison to phloretic acid, the absolute score of allyl phenol is reduced by the weighted score, mainly due to the availability of raw materials, which is one of the most important aspects of this material selection. This underlines the described critical influence of the requirement weighting in MCDM (Zhang et al., 2017). However, the sensitivity analysis of the effect of the change of the requirement weights emphasizes the overall robustness of the results (SI 2 Table S4 and Fig. S2). To provide additional guidance on the definition of weights, Mat-STAP incorporates the sustainability share as an integrated method, enabling subjective, simple, and transparent adjustments to requirement weightings in the context of sustainability. This indicates that allyl phenol is the most promising bio-based phenol for the development of bio-based benzoxazines. Both allyl phenol and phloretic acid show particular advantages regarding the energy consumption of the synthesis, reaction temperature and time, as well as the price of the raw materials, the recyclability of solvents and the scalability.

An ongoing investigation focuses on the synthesis of benzoxazines from both allyl phenol and phloretic acid as the most promising phenolic feedstock options to validate and compare their performance in terms of sustainability and project-specific material requirements.

4. Conclusions

The implementation of sustainable practises at an early stage of the product development is crucial to enable sustainable results and mitigate risks across the development process and product life cycle. Given the multidisciplinary and complex nature of material development, the

Fig. 6. Weighted results for the rating of each potential solution for bio-based benzoxazine synthesis in the respective pre-defined requirements.

adoption of comprehensive, collaborative, and efficient guidelines, tools, and practices is essential, while minimising resource-intensive efforts.

The Mat-STAP method presents an effective tool for selecting materials on a semi-quantitative level. Its applicability extends beyond a singular development stage, encompassing all phases of sustainable product development. Unlike the traditional LCA, this approach requires considerably fewer effort, while yielding semi-quantitative results at entry level to enable a sustainable material selection with respect to the project objectives. Mat-STAP's proactive nature enhances sustainability from the early on, preventing development that misses the mark, thereby saving resources. The simple structure and transparent assessment allow uncertainty to be dealt with by incorporating qualitative categories. The simple and quick decision-making can be adjusted based on the development objectives by balancing the Sustainability Share S_i with the requirement weights. The methods participative design and comprehensibility improves a collaborative workflow among stakeholders and project partners. Mat-STAP reflects a significant prospective comparative quick assessment of a variety of potential solutions for emerging technologies tailored to the scope of a project with the selection of specific indicators and requirements. While it is intended to provide project-specific sustainable solutions, it is important to note that the assessment of such solutions is not intended to be decontextualised and a respective score cannot serve as a general sustainability index. A significant and valuable addition to Mat-STAP can be the inclusion of material performance in the assessment. For a sustainable material selection, the evaluation of a potential solution e.g. based on its mechanical performance in relation to the application requirements, is of high interest and should be considered in future iterations of this method. Therefore, for each potential solution, sustainability related

indices can be compared for a selection of the most relevant material properties, improving the overall effectiveness of the assessment. Furthermore, the evaluation and integration of a structured approach to defining requirement weights can improve the Mat-STAP methodology and increase the significance of the results. A future investigation will focus on the synthesis of benzoxazines from allyl phenol and phloretic acid to validate and compare their performance in terms of sustainability and project-specific material requirements, adding another dimension to the integrated approach to assess emerging technologies for sustainable development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan-Marten Sprenger: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gideon Abels:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Katharina Haag:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Mohammad Fahad Zaki Khan:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Katharina Koschek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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